

ENGLISH AND COGNITIVE SCIENCES: EMERGENCE OF COGNITIVE PROCESSES IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

Sattarova Dilrabo Ikrambayevna

Assistant teacher of the “English” department of the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Article information:

Manuscript received: 21 Aug 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Sep 2024; **Published:** 29 Oct 2024

Abstract: This article analyzes the role and importance of cognitive processes in the process of learning English. Cognitive science studies brain activity in language learning, processes such as memory and attention. Cognitive processes in learning English are important in acquiring new vocabulary and grammatical rules. This study reveals the possibilities of improving the effectiveness of the language learning process and developing effective strategies for teachers and students. The study of the relationship between cognitive processes and language learning will help to apply innovative approaches in language education.

Keywords: English, cognitive science, language learning, memory, attention, language learning, cognitive processes, teaching, methodology, language learning, bilingualism, learners, performance, psychology, thinking, pedagogy, innovation.

Introduction

The English language has global importance, and its learning plays an important role in the personal and professional development of many people. The role of cognitive processes in the process of language learning is very large, because brain activity, memory and thinking processes are interrelated in language acquisition. Cognitive science helps improve the effectiveness of language learning by studying processes such as human thinking, attention, and memory. This article analyzes in detail the occurrence of cognitive processes and their influence in the process of learning English. This study provides the necessary scientific basis to further improve language learning strategies and help develop students' cognitive potential.

Main part

The process of learning English is not only learning new words, but cognitive processes, that is, different parts of the brain, work in this process. Cognitive processes include many elements such as memory, attention and thinking. Memory is important in the language learning process, and how students learn new words and phrases and how they commit them to memory are interrelated. Research shows that learned information is reinforced in memory through repetition and viewing. These processes help students develop effective strategies for introducing new vocabulary and grammar rules.

According to the theories of cognitive psychology, the process of language learning consists of many stages, and at each stage, different aspects of brain activity are activated. In the first stage, new information is introduced and it is received with attention and attention. Attention helps you focus on important information and learn more effectively. Students may have difficulty absorbing multiple pieces of information at once, so it's important to create an

environment that encourages students to focus.

Memory is another important aspect in the language learning process, which is necessary for the retention of new words and phrases. In order to remember the learned words and grammatical rules, it is necessary to strengthen the memory processes of students. Giving students the opportunity to regularly repeat new words and apply them in their own lives helps strengthen memory. For example, when learning new words, using them in a context or using them to create a story enhances memory processes.

Bilingualism, that is, knowledge of two languages, develops human cognitive abilities. Bilingual individuals have more flexibility in making connections between the first language and the second language. Bilingualism's connection with cognitive processes helps students develop their thinking skills during the language learning process. Students become more comfortable learning a new language by adapting their knowledge of their mother tongue to English. The fact that bilingual individuals are able to think in multiple languages that they are comfortable with also enhances their logical thinking.

Approaches based on cognitive science include various methods to make the language learning process more effective. Active learning methods involve students in their activities and help them feel special. For example, techniques such as group discussions, interactive dialogues, and role-playing can help students develop interpersonal relationships. In these processes, students will have the opportunity to put their knowledge into practice.

Innovative approaches, for example, through artificial intelligence and online learning platforms, help to further study cognitive processes. These technologies increase the interactivity in the language learning process and increase the students' interest. For example, learning resources powered by artificial intelligence provide students with an individualized learning experience and allow them to develop curricula tailored to their needs. These processes help to develop the cognitive potential of students and make the process of language learning more interesting.

The study of cognitive processes during language learning not only helps in the acquisition of knowledge, but is also important in the general development of students. Explaining to students the interdependence of cognitive processes and actively teaching them will lead to effective results in the development of their language learning skills. Thus, analysis of the role and importance of cognitive processes in the process of learning English opens opportunities for improving language learning strategies for teachers and students.

The role and importance of cognitive processes in the process of learning English should be strongly analyzed in several ways. It is important for students to gain a deeper understanding of attention, memory, and cognitive processes involved in language learning in order to acquire knowledge more effectively. This topic provides a scientific basis that helps to further improve the educational process and support the personal development of students.

Conclusion

This article analyzed the role and importance of cognitive processes in the process of learning English. Important aspects such as cognitive processes, memory and attention play an important role in increasing the effectiveness of the language learning process. In order for learned words and grammatical rules to be stored in memory, students' attention and activity is required. With the help of cognitive sciences, opportunities for improving language learning strategies and applying innovative approaches are opened. The study of cognitive processes is important not only in language learning, but also in the general development of students. The emergence and influence of cognitive processes during language learning provides the necessary scientific basis for making the educational system more effective.

The list of literature

1. Anderson, J.R. (2005). *Cognitive Psychology and Its Implications*. Worth Publishers. 672 pages.
2. Ellis, R. (2008). *The Study of Second Language Acquisition*. Oxford University Press. 372 pages.
3. O'Malley, J. M., & Chamot, A. U. (1990). *Learning Strategies in Second Language Acquisition*. Cambridge University Press. 208 pages.
4. Swain, M. (2000). The Output Hypothesis and Beyond: Mediating Acquisition through Collaborative Dialogue. In *Sociocultural Theory and Second Language Learning* (pp. 97-114). Oxford University Press. 218 pages.
5. Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes*. Harvard University Press. 159 pages.